

THE INFLUENCE OF STEAM TECHNOLOGY ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Ashurova Zarina Muxitdinovna

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute,
teacher of the department of preschool education

Annotation. The article describes the emergence of STEAM technology in education, definitions of STEAM technology by scientists from the Commonwealth of Independent States and developed countries, as well as the meaning of the STEAM abbreviation.

Keywords. STEAM technology, science - science, technology - technology, reading - reading, engineering - engineering, art - art.

Around the world, quality preschool education is defined as an important investment in the development of human capital, ensuring its achievements in public life. Based on international experience, the use of technologies that ensure the mental potential, emotional and physical health of children in the educational process, raising the quality of school education to a new level, innovative approaches expressed in the UN sustainable development goals until 2030. A significant improvement was noted as one of the main indicators process based on the use of STEAM technology.

Large-scale scientific and practical research on organizing and managing the effectiveness of preschool education organizations in our country based on modern requirements, increasing the competence of teachers, identifying factors that ensure the effectiveness of reforms in the preschool education system, and applying them to the process is underway. These studies are based on the introduction of modern methods of intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of preschool children, the development of mechanisms for using high-quality preschool education, which is an important resource for the development of all spheres of a child's life. In life and work, STEAM technology is based on world experience.

Leading issues of improving methods of preparing children for school while enriching the content of the didactic application system. From this point of view, in the learning process, determining the child's level of development, readiness for primary education, social, personal, emotional, speech, physical and creative abilities based on assessment, the application of metacognitive skills forming a cluster, educational and important tasks. such as the creation of alternative forms of education. At the same time, it is necessary to satisfy the needs of subjects of preschool education, develop the abilities, talents, internal capabilities of children, unique individual psychological characteristics, improve the theoretical and methodological foundations for ensuring the comprehensive development of children based on the use of STEAM technology, as well as improving the quality of education and developing a system that justifies harmony of efficiency is becoming increasingly important.

Scientists from Uzbekistan I.N. Kim, Y.R. Makhmutazimova on the topic of using STEAM technologies in preschool educational organizations and M.Kh. Tashibaeva, G.O. Abduraimova application of STEAM technology in primary education; M.I. Sayfullaeva, Sh.R. Turdiev, M.F. Jumanazarova, O.A. Toychiev, T.L. Khurvalieva, Z.B. Sangirova conducted research on the use of STEAM technology in various fields of education. On the use of STEAM technology in preschool education in the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States. Volosoves, V.A. Markova, S.A. Averin, V.A. Khachaturova, G. Bogdanovich, Yu.V. Karpova, T.S. Kochurina, L.L. Lashkova, E.A. Chance, D.N. Shtanko, Yu.A. Kuzmina, T.V. Timofeeva, Zh.A. Gorbunova, M.E. Filimonova, N.M. Sobol, O.I. Roshchupkina, O.V. Kireeva conducted the research.

In foreign countries D. Ahn, J. Moon, S. Singer, S. Wahyuningsih, N. Nurjana, U. Endang, R. Hafida, A. Pudyaningtyas, M. Syamsuddin, K. Lindeman, M. Jabot, M. Berkeley , O. Monkievičienė, H. Clements, J. Sarama, F. Jamil, S. Linder, D. Stegelin, K. DeJarnette, J. Aldemir, H. Kermani, D. Samara on STEAM technology in preschool education and M. Stohlmann , T. Moore, G. Roehring, J. Martinez, C. Kangas, K. Sormenen, T. Korhonen, J. Gonzalez, J. Kuenzi, A. Juskeviciene, V. Dagien, V. Dolgopologas J. Breiner, S. Harkness, K. Johnson, K. Koehler conducted

research on the application of STEAM technology in various fields of education. It is known that STEAM education occupies a central place in modern education. Particular attention is paid to the use of open, flexible, individualized, modern educational technologies based on the application, development and dissemination of information technologies and innovative educational programs in the scientific system STEM, STEAM, STREM.

Among the researchers working in our country, I.N. Kim: “Today, the global trend in education is the concept of STEAM, which is based on the nature of practical training and the integration of technical, humanities and creativity. The main requirement of STEAM education is continuity of education, as well as cooperation of students with each other and with adults, which ensures the generation of unique ways to complete assigned tasks,” he described STEAM technology.

Sh.R. Turdiev In his study, described the use of STEAM technology in education: “Each of the subjects included in the STEAM subjects is a whole subject with a separate source of knowledge. If we pay attention to the history of the emergence of these sciences, we can see the emergence of another science as a result of the rapid development of one science. Thus, it is important to use integrated education when applying theoretical knowledge in practice. As a result of the implementation of such education, learning and integration of STEAM subjects will occur.

M.H. Tashibaeva “STEAM - educational technology is based on collective, group and individual experience aimed at acquiring practical knowledge through contexts, electronic means, distribution and natural means that ensure the mutual integration of various modern methods and forms of learning for participants.” educational process. is a project activity,” explained STEAM technology.

Among the researchers working in our country, G.I. Sayfullaeva created the STEM program as a result of her research and defines this technology as follows: “STEM, STEAM - providing the basis for connecting the growing network of educational sciences, business and society, developing student interest in the natural and technical sciences, it is a technology that accomplishes such tasks as the love of doing one’s work, which serves as the basis for the development of interests.”

American researchers J. Moon and S.R. Singers described it: “STEAM technology is a technology that simultaneously integrates theoretical and practical learning into the classroom and teaches science in an extremely deep way.”

Indonesian scientists S. Wahyuningsih, N.E. Nurjana, Yu.E. Endang, R. Hafida, A.R. Pudyaningtyas, M.M. Syamsuddinlar: “With the help of STEAM, objects are not combined into separate networks, but also show the relationship of objects with everyday life, and reveal children's creativity. That is, in STEAM technology, children learn to show their creativity by solving several interrelated problems while completing a given task. With the help of such tasks, the child not only comes up with ideas, but also learns to implement them in everyday life. Thus, the child learns to solve his activities independently within the limits of the task and available opportunities.

Brad Smith, a Microsoft executive, said, “There is currently a shortage of scientists who are both technical and natural science savvy”.

Shtanko Dmitry Nikolaevich, one of the Russian scientists, in his study stated that “STEAM technology in preschool education will help our children become the next generation of inventors and leaders, conduct research like scientists, model like technologists, create designs like engineers.”

STEAM technology in education was created in the 90s of the 20th century in the United States of America. The abbreviation STEAM originally had the form STEM, and in 2006, the US President reformed the country’s education sector, including the issue of teacher training in STEM technologies in the US national curriculum.

In the 1990s, Robert Rutberstein, a professor at the University of Michigan in America, devoted his entire life to finding ways to teach children about exploration and science. As a result of his research, he came to the conclusion that the right hemisphere of the human brain is responsible for creative thinking, and the left hemisphere for logical thinking. According to Robert Rutberstein, all inventors who knew the technical sciences well were interested in art. Taking this into account, American researchers added the field of “Art” to STEM technology. Art is a tool

that reveals the hidden, inner abilities of preschool children, developing talent and talent.

In the United States, STEM technology has become a subject in higher education after the development of an educational project. The most famous example of such universities is the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in the USA. The motto of this institute is “Mens et Manus” (“Mind and Hand”). MIT has developed STEM courses and even created STEM learning centers at some institutions to give students the opportunity to promote STEM concepts and be exposed to new technologies. During the activities of this event, experimental groups on STEM technology were organized. In the experimental groups, a new curriculum based on STEM technology was created in an unconventional way. The schedule of students' activities in and outside of class was determined in the program.

Soon, the results of the institute's students receiving education in STEM technology in the experimental group far exceeded the results of the students in the control group. In this regard, the scope of use of STEM technologies in US education has expanded.

In the 1990s, Robert Rutberstein, a professor at the University of Michigan in America, devoted his entire life to finding ways to teach children about exploration and science. As a result of his research, he came to the conclusion that the right hemisphere of the human brain is responsible for creative thinking, and the left hemisphere for logical thinking. According to Robert Rutberstein, all inventors who knew the technical sciences well were interested in art. Taking this into account, American researchers added the field of “Art” to STEM technology. A step-by-step process for integrating STEM and STEAM technologies into education was then developed.

The “Science” area of STEAM technology includes such natural sciences as biology, zoology, anatomy, chemistry, geography, geology, and physics. The Technology area of STEAM technology includes subjects such as computer science and robotics. The Engineering field knows how to develop and apply

engineering principles. The Arts area includes visual arts, music, choreography, theater and even foreign languages. Area "Mathematics": consists of subjects such as mathematics, algebra, geometry. In conclusion, it should be said that the use of STEAM education in the development of the educational environment in the world community is recognized as the best technology in the processes of modern globalization, and the task of this technology is to improve the quality of education. and meet the requirements. modern requirements. The requirements and needs are to make students natural, increase their interest in technical sciences and develop their knowledge. STEAM education is the most effective and convenient technology recognized in world experience, and the feasibility of using this teaching and learning, starting from preschool educational institutions, is a pressing issue today. In this regard, a special place is occupied by improving the didactic capabilities of a developmental environment based on STEAM technology in preschool educational institutions.

Bibliography:

1. Clements H.D., Sarama J. STEM or STEAM or STREAM? Integrated or Interdisciplinary? //Embedding STEAM in early childhood education and care. – Cham : Springer International Publishing, 2021. – C. 261-275.
2. DeJarnette N.K. Implementing STEAM in the early childhood classroom // European Journal of STEM Education. – 2018. – T. 3. – №. 3. – C. 18.
3. Honey M., Pearson G., Schweingruber H. (Eds.). (2014). STEM integration in K-12 education: Status, prospects, and an agenda for research, 500. Washington, DC: National Academies Press. doi: 10.17226/18612
4. Jamil F.M., Linder S.M., Stegelin D.A. Early childhood teacher beliefs about STEAM education after a professional development conference //Early childhood education journal. – 2018. – T. 46. – C. 409-417.
5. Jarnette De., Implementing N. K. STEAM in the early childhood classroom //European Journal of STEM Education. – 2018. – T. 3. – №. 3. – C. 18.

6. Kim I.N. “Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalar ekologik ta’limida STEAM-texnologiyalardan foydalanish” Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (phd) dissertatsiyasi avtoreferati T.: 2023.

7. Marmon M. The emergence of the creativity in STEM: fostering an alternative approach for Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Instruction through the use of the arts //STEAM education: theory and practice. – 2019. – C. 101-115.

8. Martinez J.E. The search for method in STEAM education. – Springer International Publishing, 2017. – C. 111-125.

9. Monkeviciene O. et al. Impact of innovative STEAM education practices on teacher professional development and 3-6 year old children’s competence development //Journal of Social Studies Education Research. – 2020. – T. 11. – №. 4. – C. 1-27.

10. Ashurova Z. Scientific prodress: Muammoli ta’lim texnologiyalari, ularning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari //Buxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti jurnali. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 1.

11. Ashurova Z. M. Using STEAM Technology in Preschool Education //European journal of innovation in nonformal education. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 6. – C. 6-10.

12. Ashurova Z. M. “INSECTS”(PRACTICAL LESSON FOR PRESCHOOLERS) //International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 86-92.

13. Muxiddinovna A. Z. The Place and Importance of Steam Educational Technology in Preschool Education //Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices. – 2022. – T. 11. – C. 3-5.

14. Ashurova Z. M. Maktabgacha ta’limda STEAM ta’lim texnologiyasining ahamiyati //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 233-235.

15. Ashurova Z. M. Maktabgacha ta'lim natijadorligini oshirishda STEAM texnologiyasini qo'llashning ahamiyati //Science and Education. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 7. – С. 164-170.
16. Ashurova Z. M. Methodology for organizing training based on steam technology in preschool education (practical lesson for preschoolers) //International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 99-104.
17. Muxitdinovna A. Z. Mantessori Preschool Organizations //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 1. – С. 373-377.
18. Ashurova Z. Pedagogik mahorat: Maktabgacha ta'limda STEAM texnologiyasidan foydalanish samaradorligini aniqlashga oid tajriba sinov ishlari tahlili //Buxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti jurnali. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 2.
19. Muxitdinovna A. Z. Pedagogning fasilitatorlik faoliyati-ta'lim sifatini kafolatlash omili //Научно-практическая конференция. – 2021.
20. Ashurova Z. Таълим ва инновацион tadqiqotlar образование и инновационные исследования education and innovative research: таълим ва инновацион tadqiqotlar образование и инновационные исследования education and innovative research //Buxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti jurnali. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 1.
21. Muxitdinovna A. Z. Pedagogning fasilitatorlik faoliyati-ta'lim sifatini kafolatlash omili //Научно-практическая конференция. – 2021.
22. Muxitdinovna A. Z. Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari tarbiyachilarining bolalar bilan faoliyatlarni tashkil etishdagi fasilitatorlik tayyorgarligi //barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 3. – С. 343-347.
23. Ashurova Z. M. Methodology for organizing training based on steam technology in preschool education (practical lesson for preschoolers) //International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 99-104.

24. Ashurova Z. M. Maktabgacha ta'lim natijadorligini oshirishda STEAM texnologiyasini qo'llashning ahamiyati //Science and Education. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 7. – С. 164-170
25. Ashurova Z. M. Maktabgacha ta'limda STEAM ta'lim texnologiyasining ahamiyati //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 233-235.
26. Muxiddinova A. Z. The Place and Importance of Steam Educational Technology in Preschool Education //Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices. – 2022. – T. 11. – С. 3-5.
27. Ashurova Z. Jahon maktabgacha ta'lim rivojida noan'anaviy mashg'ulotlar: Valdorf, Montessori pedagogikasi //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. Uz). – 2020. – T. 4. – №. 4.
28. Ashurova Z. Boshlang'ich ta'lim sifat va samaradorligini oshirish: strategiya, innovatsiya va ilg'or tajribalar: Pedagogning fasilitatorlik faoliyati ta'lim sifatini kafolatlash garovi //Buxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti jurnali. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 1.
29. Muxitdinova A. Z. Zamonaviy ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida fasilitorning o'rni: Ashurova Zarina Muxitdinova, buxdu mustaqil izlanuvchisi //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 2. – С. 215-219
30. Ashurova Z. Pedagogik Mahorat//ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. Uz).–2021.
31. Ashurova Z. M. “Insects”(practical lesson for preschoolers) //International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 86-92.
32. To'raqulovich J. U. C. 215-218. 5//To'raqulovich, JU, & Muxitdinova, AZ Features of Speech Development in Children of Middle Preschool Age //Т. – T. 6. – С. 23-25

33. Muxitdinovna Z. A. Et al. Features of the Development of Speech in Preschoolers //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 1. – С. 245-251